

resistance scales of these types are significantly lower than that of other types. In terms of average resistance, Yunnan rices could be classified into three significantly different resistance groups.

Presence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in xylem cells of tungro-infected rice

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Earlier studies have shown that RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) are restricted to the phloem tissues of infected plants, and it has been suggested that only phloem feeding by green leafhopper (GLH) causes tungro infection. On GLH-resistant cultivars, however, it has been observed that GLH feeds mainly from the xylem and transmits primarily RTBV. We examined the location of RTBV in host cells in relation to tungro transmission.

Rice seedlings (15 d old) of tungro-susceptible cultivar TN1 and GLH-resistant cultivar ASD8 were inoculated with rice tungro viruses (RTVs) using adult GLHs. The leaf blades of infected plants were collected 30 d after inoculation for electron microscope study.

RTBV particles were found in xylem parenchyma cells as well as in phloem

Table 2. Distribution of resistant varieties in 8 classes and the significance level test of mean resistance scales.

Classification	Total (no.)	Resistant varieties		Mean resistance scale ^a
		no.	%	
Indica-irrigated-nonglutinous	1832	65	3.55	8.02 b
Indica-irrigated-glutinous	303	17	5.61	7.76 b
Indica-upland-nonglutinous	31	0	0	8.35 a
Indica-upland-glutinous	20	1	5.00	7.80 b
Japonica-irrigated-nonglutinous	679	70	10.31	7.38 c
Japonica-irrigated-glutinous	419	50	11.93	7.26 c
Japonica-upland-nonglutinous	641	24	3.74	7.96 b
Japonica-upland-glutinous	166	15	9.04	7.39 c
Total	4091	242	5.92	

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

cells of tungro-infected TN1 and ASD8 (see figure). RTSV was observed only in phloem cells and around the boundary between xylem and phloem tissues. In initial observations, RTBV in xylem cells were found in the third and fourth leaf position of infected plants.

These results suggest that GLH can transmit RTBV directly to xylem cells, where the virus multiplies and causes infection. They also support the observation that GLH feeds mainly from the xylem of GLH-resistant cultivars and transmits predominantly RTBV. □

RTBV in xylem parenchyma cells of rice cultivars TN1 (a) and ASD8 (b). R = ribosomes.

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Four upland rice varieties released in Sierra Leone

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The uplands account for about 70% of the rice area in Sierra Leone. In 1988, four new varieties (ROK17, ROK18, ROK19, ROK20), all foreign introductions, were released for upland planting (Table 1). These varieties surpassed check variety ROK16 in overall performance and farmer acceptability in field tests over four seasons.

Table 1. Mean performance of 4 newly released varieties in Sierra Leone.

Variety	Original name	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)
ROK17	LAC23	119	138	186	3.1
ROK18	IDSA-6	96	117	174	2.9
ROK19	FARROX 299	116	115	172	2.8
ROK20	IRAT161	103	118	178	3.0
ROK16	NGOVIE (local)	128	132	183	2.6

In varietal trials conducted for two seasons in farmers' fields in three villages in the North-Western Region, the new varieties consistently outyielded local check ROK16. Table 2 shows grain yields and some properties of the soils.

ROK17 is a local japonica selection from Liberia. It is a medium-duration cultivar, with bold grains much like ROK16. It is, however, more resistant to diseases and lodging than ROK16 and is suited to the high rainfall areas of East